

ANALYSIS OF PHONETIC CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TEXT OF NAVOY'S WORKS

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Abstract: the article analyzes the lexical and semantic features of homonymous words in the work of Alisher Navoi on the basis of linguistics.

Keywords: method, principle, text, work, homonymous, analysis, words.

Alisher Navoi gave valuable information about the consonants in our classical script in his works “Majolis un-nafais”, “Muhokamat ul-lughatayn”. As a result of collecting and organizing them, necessary information can be obtained about vocalism and consonantism of the 15th century - our classical writing.

For example, the poet says the following about the qualitative characteristics of the vowel **a**. “... In one of those sentences, Alif (ا) and Ho (ه) have a relationship and communication, so that even a word can be rhymed with an Alif word at the end. It's just that the word “yado” (يدا) can be rhymed with “sado” (صدا) and “boda” (پادە) can also be rhymed” [Alisher Navoi, 2000:19].

With the help of this example, the poet informs that there are two vowels **a** in the old Uzbek language, one of them is the normal long sound **a**, represented by the symbol alif (ا), the second one is hoy hawwaz (ه) and the other is the short vowel **a**, which is not distinguished by meaning. And finally, if we take into account the words “almishtur”, “atsa”, “aghuluq”, which are found in the poet's works, including in the poet's autograph of Alisher Navoi, which is kept in the royal library in Tehran, it is

written with the alif mamduda (ا) at the beginning of the word: almishtur, atsa, aggluq, it is known that there were three types of vowel a in the 15th century [Sh. Shukurov, 1990:36-43].

Speaking about the labeled vowel, Navoi emphasizes that there were four independent phonemes in the old Uzbek literary language of the 15th century, and cites the following examples: "...the net (تور) is stable, and the net (تور) is thinner than before: the one that kills the bird is weeping, and the net (تور) is thinner than the other: the net (تور) of the house and the net (تور) that is, the whole ditch: the mesh or door tormak is fictitious [Alisher Navoi, 2000:19].

As can be seen from these examples, Navoi states that there are four independent phonemes in the old Uzbek language that differ from each other in terms of length and length. The first of them has a normal length **o** (تور - a house), the second (تور - a wood on which a bird sits) is a short **u*** of the first degree because it is shorter than the first one, and the third (تور - a web of a house) is a short **u** of the second degree because it is shorter than the second one; the fourth [Alisher Navoiy, 2000:19] (تور - web, the web of the door) is shorter than the third, so it is a short **u** of the third degree.

The poet also left valuable information about the vowel **i** in the 15th century: "Va yoyiy misol uch harakatdan ortiq topilmas: ter (تير) ki, termak ma'nisi biladir. Ter (تير) ki, andin daqiqdur, uldurki, sortlar oni "araq" va "xuy" derlar. Ter (تير) ki, boridin ariqdur, o'q ma'nosi biladir"[Alisher Navoiy, 2000:19]. These examples show that in the old Uzbek language of the 15th century, there were three **i** vowels that differed from each other in length and length and had the characteristic of meaning separation. Of these, we took the vowel **i** in the first word as **ie**, in the

* Alisher Navoiy asarlariga bag'ishlab tuzilgan "Badoye' ul-lug'at" ma'lumotlariga asosanib ikkinchi, uchinchi va to'rtinchi fonemalar – **u** qilib olindi.

second word there is a simple long *i*, in the third there is a long *i* phoneme [Alisher Navoi, 2000:19].

So, in the language of Navoi's works, i.e. the old Uzbek language of the 15th century, there were 12 vowel sounds. Nine of them have the phoneme feature (a, o', u - short of the first degree, u - short of the second degree, u - short of the third degree i, ie, i; e), the remaining three (long ä, short a and i) are excluded from this feature. In addition, the spelling of vowels in the language of written monuments, especially the spelling and functions of the letters alif (a), vov (w), yo (y) have been analyzed in detail one by one by some Turkic scholars in their scientific articles [Sh. Shukurov, 1990:19-24]. But further studies confirm that there are not 12 but 10 vowels in the classical Uzbek language [E.Umarov, 2009:28]. They differed from each other in terms of length and brevity: a: - a, i: -i, u: -u, o': -o', e: -e [E. Umarov, 2017:30]. It shows that there were 31 consonants [E.Umarov, 2017:30].

The formal expression of words and phrases in manuscripts, in particular, the occurrence of changes in sound structure, phonetic variants, is not a simple matter. It is based on such principles as the laws of the internal development of the text, the environment of the time, the interaction of languages, the introduction of new words and expressions, and the progress of science and technology. Therefore, in the process of converting them, it is permissible to study these phonetic cases in depth. In this regard, it is appropriate to talk about the orthographic features of some Turkish words in Navoi's works created in the 14-15 centuries.

In conclusion, in order to ensure that the standards of the old Uzbek literary language are followed in the analysis of words and phrases with phonetic variants in translation, it is necessary to take into account textual studies, the history of the Uzbek language, as well as the original language features of the works of some classic representatives of our literature and dictionaries created in previous centuries.

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